

**ФУНДАМЕНТАЛ ВА
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**ВЕСТНИК ФУНДАМЕНТАЛЬНОЙ И
КЛИНИЧЕСКОЙ МЕДИЦИНЫ**

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ABORTION AND ITS IMPACT ON THE REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH OF WOMEN OF REPRODUCTIVE AGE**Raximjonova G.R., Indiaminova G.N.**

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Resume. This article analyzes, based on current scientific evidence, the short- and long-term effects of induced termination of pregnancy (abortion) on women's reproductive health. The socio-demographic determinants, epidemiological characteristics, and clinical features of both spontaneous and induced abortion are examined. Particular attention is given to the impact of pharmacological, vacuum aspiration, and instrumental methods of induced abortion on endometrial structure, with special emphasis on the pathogenetic mechanisms underlying basal layer injury. Early and late post-abortion complications are described, including chronic endometritis, intrauterine adhesions (Asherman syndrome), ovarian dysfunction, luteal phase deficiency, and the risk of infertility. Neuroendocrine alterations within the hypothalamic–pituitary–ovarian axis, hormonal imbalance, and the dynamics of ovarian reserve parameters are also discussed. Furthermore, the impact of abortion on subsequent pregnancies is analyzed, particularly in relation to cervical insufficiency, placental pathologies, ectopic pregnancy, and the risk of preterm birth. The importance of a comprehensive post-abortion care system in restoring reproductive function is emphasized.

Keywords: abortion, reproductive health, post-abortion complications, chronic endometritis, Asherman syndrome, endometrial receptivity, hypothalamic–pituitary–ovarian axis, hormonal imbalance, luteal phase deficiency, ovarian reserve, anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH), infertility, placental pathology, cervical insufficiency, post-abortion care (PAC).

АБОРТ ВА УНИНГ ФЕРТИЛ ЁШДАГИ АЁЛЛАР РЕПРОДУКТИВ САЛОМАТЛИГИГА ТАЪСИРИ**Рахимжонова Г.Р., Индиаминова Г.Н.**

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Резюме. Мазкур мақолада ҳомиладорликни сунъий тўхтатишининг (аборт) аёл репродуктив саломатлигига кўрсатадиган қисқа ва узоқ муддатли таъсири илмий манбалар асосида таҳлил қилинган. Абортнинг ижтимоий-демографик омиллари, эпидемиологик хусусиятлари ҳамда спонтан ва сунъий шакллари клиник жиҳатлари ёритилган. Сунъий абортнинг фармакологик, вакуум-аспирация ва инструментал усуллари эндометрий тузилмасига таъсири, айниқса базал қатлам шикастланишининг патогенетик механизмлари чуқур таҳлил қилинган. Постаборттив даврда ривожланадиган эрта ва кеч асоратлар, жумладан сурункали эндометрит, бачадон ичи битишмалари (Ашерман синдроми), тухумдон дисфункцияси, лутеал фаза етишимовчилиги ҳамда инфертиллик хавфи илмий далиллар асосида баён этилган. Гипоталамо–гипофиз–тухумдон тизими фаолиятидаги нейроэндокрин ўзгаришлар, гормонал дисбаланс ва овариал резерв кўрсаткичларининг динамикаси кўриб чиқилган. Шунингдек, абортнинг кейинги ҳомиладорликларга таъсири — истмик-сервикал етишимовчилик, плацентар патологиялар, эктопик ҳомиладорлик ва муддатидан олдин тузғуқ хавфи билан боғлиқ жиҳатлари таҳлил этилган. Репродуктив функцияни тиклашда комплекс постаборттив ёрдам тизими муҳимлиги таъкидланган.

Калит сўзлар: аборт, репродуктив саломатлик, постаборттив асоратлар, сурункали эндометрит, Ашерман синдроми, эндометрий рецептивлиги, гипоталамо–гипофиз–тухумдон тизими, гормонал дисбаланс, лутеал фаза етишимовчилиги, овариал резерв, антимюллер гормони (АМГ), инфертиллик, плацентар патология, истмик-сервикал етишимовчилик, PAC (Post-Abortion Care).

АБОРТ И ЕГО ВЛИЯНИЕ НА РЕПРОДУКТИВНОЕ ЗДОРОВЬЕ ЖЕНЩИН ФЕРТИЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА**Рахимжонова Г.Р., Индиаминова Г.Н.**

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Резюме. В данной статье на основе современных научных источников проанализировано краткосрочное и отдалённое влияние искусственного прерывания беременности (аборта) на репродуктивное здоровье женщин. Освещены социально-демографические факторы, эпидемиологические особенности, а также клинические аспекты самопроизвольных и индуцированных форм аборта. Особое

внимание уделено влиянию фармакологического, вакуум-аспирационного и инструментального методов искусственного прерывания беременности на структуру эндометрия, с акцентом на патогенетические механизмы повреждения его базального слоя. Рассмотрены ранние и поздние постабортные осложнения, включая хронический эндометрит, внутриматочные синехии (Asherman syndrome), дисфункцию яичников, недостаточность лютеиновой фазы и риск бесплодия. Проанализированы нейроэндокринные изменения в системе гипоталамус–гипофиз–яичники, гормональный дисбаланс и динамика показателей овариального резерва. Также изучено влияние аборта на последующие беременности, в частности развитие истмико-цервикальной недостаточности, плацентарной патологии, эктопической беременности и риска преждевременных родов. Подчёркнута значимость комплексной системы постабортной помощи в восстановлении репродуктивной функции.

Ключевые слова: аборт, репродуктивное здоровье, постабортные осложнения, хронический эндометрит, Asherman syndrome, рецептивность эндометрия, система гипоталамус–гипофиз–яичники, гормональный дисбаланс, недостаточность лютеиновой фазы, овариальный резерв, анти-мюллеров гормон (АМГ), бесплодие, плацентарная патология, истмико-цервикальная недостаточность, постабортная помощь (РАС).

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Induced termination of pregnancy (abortion) remains one of the most complex and multifaceted challenges in modern obstetrics and gynecology. The issue of abortion encompasses not only medical aspects but also social, demographic, psychological, and ethical dimensions. According to data from the World Health Organization (WHO), millions of women worldwide undergo abortion procedures each year using various methods, with the majority occurring among women of reproductive age. Reproductive age (15–49 years) represents the most active and physiologically significant stage of the female reproductive system. Abortions performed during this period may exert both short- and long-term adverse effects on reproductive health. Statistical data indicate that abortions frequently occur in the context of unintended pregnancies, often resulting from insufficient or incorrect use of contraceptive methods.

The prevalence of abortion is strongly influenced by socio-economic determinants, including low living standards, unemployment, housing difficulties, family conflicts, and young women's desire to continue education or professional development. Limited reproductive awareness and restricted access to modern contraceptive methods further contribute to increased abortion rates.

Medically, termination of pregnancy before 22 weeks of gestation or when fetal weight does not exceed 500 grams is defined as abortion. Based on etiology, abortions are classified into spontaneous and induced forms. Spontaneous abortion occurs without medical intervention and is most commonly associated with chromosomal abnormalities of the embryo or fetus. Infectious diseases, endocrine disorders, anatomical and functional uterine pathologies, as well as extragenital somatic conditions may also contribute to its development.

Induced abortion involves deliberate termination of pregnancy using medical or surgical techniques and is performed according to specific medical indications. These include life-threatening maternal conditions, severe fetal anomalies incompatible with life, or serious chronic somatic diseases in the mother. According to recurrence, abortions may be isolated events or recurrent (two or more consecutive pregnancy losses). Recurrent abortions significantly impair reproductive potential and negatively affect subsequent pregnancies.

Depending on the technique, induced abortions are categorized as:

- Medical (pharmacological) abortion;
- Vacuum aspiration;
- Surgical (instrumental curettage).

Each method has specific advantages and limitations; however, all constitute invasive interventions to varying degrees. Regardless of technique, abortion may disrupt hormonal balance, traumatize the endometrium, and weaken immune defenses. Numerous studies demonstrate that abrupt termination of pregnancy leads to dysregulation of the hypothalamic–pituitary–ovarian (HPO) axis, resulting in menstrual irregularities, anovulatory cycles, and hormonal insufficiency. These disturbances are particularly pronounced after repeated abortions.

Post-abortion complications are divided into early and late forms. Early complications include uterine bleeding, infectious-inflammatory processes, uterine perforation, and retained products of conception. If not promptly diagnosed and managed, these conditions may progress to severe septic complications. Late complications are often chronic and significantly impair fertility. They include chronic endometritis, intrauterine

adhesions (Asherman syndrome), ovarian dysfunction, persistent menstrual disturbances, and secondary infertility.

Asherman syndrome is characterized by partial or complete obliteration of the uterine cavity due to damage to the basal layer of the endometrium and subsequent formation of intrauterine adhesions. Pathogenetically, mechanical destruction of the basal layer during curettage initiates ischemia, fibroblast activation, excessive collagen deposition, and overexpression of transforming growth factor beta (TGF- β 1), leading to irreversible fibrosis. According to the classification proposed by the European Society of Gynaecological Endoscopy, the severity ranges from mild thin adhesions (Grade I) to complete obliteration of the uterine cavity (Grade IV).

The classical clinical triad of Asherman syndrome includes hypomenstrual syndrome or amenorrhea, secondary infertility, and recurrent pregnancy loss. Statistical analyses indicate that fertility may decrease by 40–60% in affected women, while the risk of placenta accreta increases significantly.

Infectious-inflammatory processes represent another major pathogenic mechanism of post-abortion reproductive dysfunction. Instrumental dilation of the cervix and intrauterine manipulation facilitate ascending infection. Studies by McQueen et al. (2014) and Cicinelli (2015) demonstrate a high incidence of acute endometritis in the early post-abortion period, which may progress to chronic endometritis if inadequately treated. Immunohistochemical studies reveal persistent infiltration of the endometrial stroma by plasma cells, lymphocytes, and macrophages, leading to impaired endometrial receptivity.

Inflammatory mediators such as interleukins (IL-1, IL-6), tumor necrosis factor alpha (TNF- α), and reactive oxygen species contribute to degradation of implantation capacity, vascular insufficiency, and gestational failure. According to WHO and ESHRE data, nearly half of women with infertility may have underlying chronic endometritis, often associated with post-abortion infectious complications.

Abrupt termination of pregnancy also affects neuroendocrine regulation. Dysregulation of gonadotropin secretion (FSH and LH), altered FSH/LH ratio, reduced estradiol levels, and luteal phase deficiency are frequently observed in the post-abortion period. Although many hormonal disturbances resolve within 2–3 cycles, persistent dysfunction may occur after repeated invasive procedures or chronic endometrial inflammation. The impact of abortion on ovarian reserve markers such as anti-Müllerian hormone (AMH) remains controversial, with insufficient large-scale evidence confirming irreversible decline.

Previous abortions may adversely influence subsequent pregnancies through mechanisms including cervical insufficiency, abnormal placentation, placenta accreta, fetal growth restriction, intrauterine hypoxia, and increased risk of ectopic pregnancy due to tubal adhesions. Repeated surgical abortions are associated with a higher incidence of preterm birth before 34 weeks of gestation.

Implementation of comprehensive Post-Abortion Care (PAC) systems—aimed at medical rehabilitation, prevention of infection, restoration of hormonal balance, fertility preservation, and psychological support—is essential. WHO experts emphasize that many post-abortion complications arise from inadequate rehabilitation and insufficient follow-up.

Post-abortion syndrome may negatively affect long-term psychological well-being, social adaptation, and maternal motivation. Literature analysis suggests that induced abortion is not merely a localized surgical intervention but a systemic factor capable of disrupting reproductive homeostasis. Structural and functional alterations, neuroendocrine imbalance, gestational complications, and psychosomatic consequences collectively demonstrate the multifactorial long-term impact of abortion on women's reproductive health.

Conclusion. The conducted analysis demonstrates that induced termination of pregnancy exerts a multifactorial and systemic impact on the female body. Abortion should be regarded not merely as a localized surgical intervention but as a factor capable of disrupting the overall homeostasis of the reproductive system. Damage to the basal layer of the endometrium, inflammatory processes, and neuroendocrine imbalance constitute the principal pathogenetic mechanisms underlying post-abortion infertility.

Repeated instrumental abortions significantly increase the risk of intrauterine synechiae, chronic endometritis, cervical insufficiency, and placental abnormalities. In addition, disturbances in hormonal regulation may lead to luteal phase deficiency and implantation failure.

Therefore, a comprehensive, stepwise, and individualized post-abortion rehabilitation strategy is essential. To preserve reproductive function and ensure the safety of future pregnancies, it is necessary to improve integrated medical care systems that include hormonal monitoring, infection control, and psychological support.

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